

Acetoacetarylamides as Chelating Ligands: Part I. Hexacoordinated Complexes of Nickel(II) Bis Acetoacetarylamides with Amines*

A. Syamal and R. L. Dutta

Hexacoordinated complexes of nickel(II) bis acetoacetarylamides with pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline have been prepared in pure crystalline forms. Conductance measurement in methanol indicates non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The electronic absorption spectra measurements exhibit three absorption bands in the vicinity of 340, 640 and 930 m μ . The complexes are all pale blue to pale bluish green in colour and are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=3.2-3.4$ B. M.). Absorption spectra and magnetic moment identify the complexes as octahedral ones and the ligands as weak donors.

The coordination complexes of the versatile chelating ligand acetylacetonone(I) with transition metals are too wellknown¹⁻⁶. But very little is known about the complexing ability of acetoacetarylamides(II), which are close to acetylacetonone in that these have the same functional groups. The composition and instability constant of iron(III) complex of acetoacetanilide has been reported⁷. Determination of formation constant of the beryllium

complex and the dissociation constant of a series of acetoacetarylamides place these as weaker donors than acetylacetonone⁸. A gravimetric estimation of beryllium⁹, preparation of copper(II) complex including stability constant determination¹⁰ and the gravimetric estimation¹¹ with acetoacetanilide have also appeared. Recently the quasiaromatic

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character of some metallic complexes (Cr, Be, Al) of these ligands has attracted attention¹²; Some oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes of these ligands have been investigated recently in our Laboratory¹³. We wish to make a comprehensive study of the chelating ability of these ligands and this paper arising out of this programme describes the adduct formation of nickel(II) bis acetoacetarylamides with different heterocyclic bases.

Addition of concentrated ammonia to an aqueous solution containing nickel (II) chloride, acetoacetanilide (1:2) and pyridine results in the formation of pale blue precipitate, which can be recrystallised from alcohol containing a small amount of pyridine to furnish pale blue shining crystals having formula $[\text{Ni}(\text{Py})_2\text{L}_2]$ (Py=pyridine; LH=a molecule of the acetoacetanilide). Evidently nickel (II) bis acetoacetanilide is formed *in situ* and addition of ammonia favours the pH for the formation of hexa coordinated adduct. Other heterocyclic bases like β -picoline and γ picoline behave in a comparable manner. Similar complexes have also been isolated for acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide, acetoacet-*o*-toluidide and acetoacet-anisidide, the details being included in the experimental. The other method of preparation starting from nickel(II) bis acetoacetarylamides as in the case of nickel(II) bis acetylaceton¹⁴ appeared not to be smooth running as the bis chelates of the present ligands were not obtained in good yield and high purity. It may be mentioned in this context that the pyridine adduct of nickel(II) bis ethylacetoacetate¹⁵ was prepared by following a similar procedure as described in this communication; α -picoline does not form well defined compounds which may be ascribed to be the steric factor of the α -methyl group.

FIG 1. Electronic absorption spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Py})_2(\text{Acet-anil})_2]$, 0.02 M; solvent: methanol ethanol, (1:1) and a small amount of pyridine.

Electrolytic conductance measurements were completed in methanol and molar conductance values (15-20 mhos) indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The complexes reported herein pertain to $3d^8$ nickel(II) and possess a coordination number six. Magnetic moments have often been found quite distinguishing between

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octahedral and tetrahedral structures¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Whereas the moments for octahedral and high spin square-planar nickel(II) have a lower orbital contribution ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.83-3.4$ B.M.), those having a tetrahedral stereochemistry have a much higher contribution ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=3.5-4.2$ B.M.) due to orbitally degenerate ground states. The measured magnetic moments of our complexes all lie within the range 3.2-3.4 B.M., which stand for octahedral nickel(II) complexes.

TABLE I
Magnetic Susceptibility measurements

Temp=294°K

Complex	Dia. corr, $\times 10^6$	χ_M (corr) $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M)*
1. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂]	234	4690	3.32
2. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂]	239	4700	3.33
3. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]	268	4720	3.34
4. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂]	247	4685	3.29
5. [Ni (β -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂]	298	5021	3.46
6. [Ni (β -Pic) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂]	303	4445	3.24
7. [Ni (β -Pic) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]	332	4940	3.42
8. [Ni (β -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂]	311	4695	3.30
9. [Ni (γ -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂]	298	4500	3.26
10. [Ni (γ -Pic) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂]	303	4802	3.37
11. [Ni (γ -Pic) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]	332	4982	3.43
12. [Ni (γ -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂]	311	4650	3.31

where Py=pyridine; β -Pic= β -picoline; γ -Pic= γ -picoline; Acet-anil=acetoacetanilide; Acet-tol=aceto-acet-o-toluidide; Acet-Cl-anil=aceto-acet-ortho-chloroanilide and Acet-anis=aceto-acet-anisidide.

*Calculated from $\lambda_M(\text{corr})$ using Curie equation $\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.84 (\lambda_M(\text{corr}) \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$

The visible absorption spectra recorded in the region of 330-1000 m μ show three absorption bands in the vicinity of 340, 640 and 930 m μ . The spectra have been recorded in mixed alcohols both in presence and absence of respective heterocyclic bases and no marked difference has been observed.

TABLE II
Electronic absorption spectral data

Complex	Solvent	Wave number ν, cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity
1. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂]	methanol, ethanol and small amount of pyridine	29,700	320*
		$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 15,800- \\ 15,600 \\ 10,700 \end{array} \right.$	5.7
			3.2
			3.2
2. [Ni (β -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂]	methanol, ethanol and small amount of β -picoline	29,700	310*
		$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 15,800- \\ 15,400 \\ 10,700 \end{array} \right.$	5
			3.2
			3.2
3. [Ni (γ -Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂] H ₂ O	methanol, ethanol and small amount of γ -picoline	29,700	320*
		$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 16,100- \\ 15,600 \\ 10,700 \end{array} \right.$	5
			3.2
			3.2

*High molar extinction co-efficient value is due mainly to ligand.

16. Cotton and Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1962, p. 737.
 17. Miller, "Advances in Inorganic and Radiochemistry", (Editor, Emeleus and Shriver), Academic Press Inc., New York, 1962, Vol-IV, p-147.
 18. Gill and Nyholm. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997.

This points to the negligible dissociation of the complexes in the solvents used. All octahedral nickel(II) complexes generally exhibit four ligand field bands¹⁹ around 330, 540, 820 and 930 m μ due to the transitions $3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (P), $3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (F), $3A_{1g} \rightarrow 1E_g$ and $3A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{2g}$. In the cases of weak ligand fields these bands may be shifted to higher wave length, as in the case for hexaquo nickel (II)²⁰, hexa (amide) nickel(II)²¹ complexes to mention only a few such cases. A critical survey of the spectra of octahedral nickel(II) complexes with a large number of strong field and also weak field ligands have led to generalisation^{19, 22, 23} that the ratio $\nu_3 : \nu_1$, ranges from 1.6-1.8. In this context, we wish to refer to some recent studies on nickel(II) octahedral complexes²³, where the author has taken this ratio as 1.82. The ratio 1.82 has been erroneously attributed to Manch and Fernelius¹⁹ irrespective of the nature of the ligands and has been utilised as a token for the identification of the stereochemistry of the complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{NH}_3)_4]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2\text{en}_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{NH}_3)_4]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{HCOO})_2\text{en}_2]$ etc. We wish to point out that this ratio cannot remain the same irrespective of the types of the ligands but has to vary within a range. Indeed Manch and Fernelius¹⁹ had given a range 1.6-1.8 instead of only 1.82 as taken by Gopal Narain. This range (1.6-1.8) has provided us with a clue to the location of the fourth absorption band in our complexes. Assuming the 930 m μ band as the ν_1 band, the ν_3 band should be located around 520-580 m μ . This region in the spectra of our complexes is situated on the descending part of 340 m μ band and thus cannot be taken to stand for the ν_3 band. Instead if we take the 640 m μ band as the ν_3 band then the above token provides the 1020-1100 m μ region as standing for the ν_1 absorption band. Since our spectrophotometer did not allow measurement beyond 1000 m μ we are unable to locate this useful band. However, this study undoubtedly points to weak donor ability of the ligands, the ν_1 band being around 8700-9800 cm^{-1} , the existence of which is indicated by the spectra exhibiting an upward trend beyond 970 m μ . Further the intensities of the absorption bands are quite low (≈ 6) and are typical of octahedral nickel (II) complexes but unlike those usually found for tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes (≈ 200 for the visible peak).²¹

In general the complexes described in this paper were not found soluble in a suitable solvent for cryoscopic determination of molecular weight.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate was a B.D.H.'s product. Pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline were Hopkin & William's (London) product. Acetoacetanilide, aceto-acet-ortho-chloroanilide, aceto-acet-o-toluidide and aceto-acetanisidide were B.D.H. (England) L. R. Variety and used directly. Methanol used was of E. Merck's G. R. Variety.

General method of preparation of the nickel(II) complexes: $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002M) was dissolved in minimum amount of water. Aceto-acet-arylamide (0.004M) was dissolved in minimum amount of heterocyclic base. These two solutions were mixed and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7.5 by addition of concentrated aqueous ammonia drop

19. Manch and Fernelius, *J. Chem. Educn.*, 1961, **38**, 192.

20. Cotton and Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1962, p. 735-738.

21. Drago, Meek, Jocston and Laroshe, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 124.

22. Rosenthal and Drago. *ibid.*, 1965, **4**, 840.

23. Gopal Narain, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1966, **39**, 2298; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 443.

by drop with stirring. Pale blue to pale bluish green precipitate formed* were filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol containing a small amount of heterocyclic base. The adducts of nickel(II) bis acetoacetanilide were not recrystallised due to their gel formation in presence of alcohol. In some cases where a large amount of heterocyclic base was needed for the dissolution of the reagents, the reagent was dissolved in ethanolic pyridine and the adducts were isolated after partial evaporation of the solvent under a fan. The complexes were all dried in air.

TABLE III

Analysis and physical properties of the nickel(II) complexes

Complex	Colour	Found %	Reqd. %
1. [Ni Py] ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂	Pale blue shining crystals	Ni, 10.3 N, 9.9	10.3 % 9.8
2. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂	Pale blue.	Ni, 9.8 N, 9.5	9.8 9.3
3. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂] 0.5H ₂ O	Pale blue	Ni, 9.0 N, 8.5 H ₂ O* 1.2	9.1 8.6 1.3
4. [Ni (Py) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂]H ₂ O	Pale bluish green	Ni, 9.3 N, 8.8 H ₂ O*, 3.0	9.1 8.6 2.7
5. [Ni (β-Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂	Pale bluish green silky crystals	Ni, 9.7 N, 9.5	9.8 9.3
6. [Ni (β-Pic) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂	Pale blue	Ni, 9.6 N, 8.8	9.4 8.9
7. [Ni (β-Pic) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂] H ₂ O	Pale blue	Ni, 8.7 N, 8.1 H ₂ O*, 2.6	8.6 8.1 2.6
8. [Ni (β-Pic) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂	Pale bluish green	Ni, 9.1 N, 8.7	8.9 8.5
9. [Ni (γ-Pic) ₂ (Acet-anil) ₂] H ₂ O	Pale blue shining crystals	Ni, 9.6 N, 9.3 H ₂ O*, 2.6	9.5 9.1 2.9
10. [Ni (γ-Pic) ₂ (Acet-tol) ₂	Pale blue	Ni, 9.5 N, 9.0	9.4 8.9
11. [Ni (γ-Pic) ₂ (Acet-Cl-anil) ₂]	Pale bluish green	Ni, 8.5 N, 8.4	8.7 8.2
12. [Ni (γ-Pic) ₂ (Acet-anis) ₂	Pale bluish green	Ni, 8.5 N, 8.4 H ₂ O* 3.0	8.7 8.2 2.6

*by loss at 110°C

General properties of nickel(II) complexes: The complexes are insoluble in water, benzene but soluble in methanol and ethanol. They do not decompose and do not liberate the heterocyclic bases even on heating up to 110°C for hours.

*Cooling in ice for few minutes appeared favourable.

General experimental procedure: Nickel was estimated by decomposing the complex by boiling with concentrated HCl for half an hour and finally precipitating nickel with dimethylglyoxime.

Nitrogen was estimated by the semimicro Duma's combustion technique. Conductance measurements were done in methanol solution with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in mixed alcohols (methanol, ethanol, 1:1) containing small amount of heterocyclic base with the help of a Hilger Watts Uvispek spectrophotometer using one cm cells.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were taken in a Gouy Magnetic Balance using recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate as calibrant and applying a field strength of about 7.9×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic correction of the ligands was determined by the use of Pascal's constants²⁴.

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
WEST BENGAL, INDIA.

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